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TEACHERS' HOME VISITATION PRACTICES IN JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL IN GUIPING CITY, GUANGXI, CHINA

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to investigate the Home Visitation Practices of junior high school teachers in Guiping City, Guangxi, and the challenges in their Home Visitation Practices and the actions they made to address the challenges.

The survey results showed that junior high school teachers in Guiping City, Guangxi have done a good job in Home Visitation Practices, but there are still many challenges in their Home Visitation Practices, involving school level, teacher level, family level and community level. Participants took a series of positive actions to address the challenges. It can be seen from the actions they took that the challenges faced in Home Visitation Practices need to be solved and overcome by the concerted efforts of schools, teachers, families and communities.

Keywords: Home Visitations, Home Visitation Practices, Junior High School, Action, Plan, Teachers

Introduction

Teachers' Home Visitations have a special educational effect, which can effectively promote the cooperation between family and school as well as establish a close and harmonious relationship among teachers, parents and children. V.O. Sukhomlynskyi, the famous educator of the former Soviet Union, once said: "The perfect education is the combination of school and family". The international community attached great importance to family-school cooperation, as well as the practices of Teachers' Home Visitations and previous related research, which brought great enlightenment to conduct this study.

In order to achieve the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal-4 - Quality Education, countries around the world are constantly striving to improve their education systems, ensure that all girls and boys complete quality primary and secondary education leading to relevant and Goal-4 effective learning outcomes. And China is no exception. In recent years, China has issued a series of educational policies, regulations and educational documents, which have put forward requirements and guidance for Teachers' Home Visitations.

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In January 2023, the Ministry of Education of China and other 13 departments jointly issued the Opinions on Improving the Family-School-Community Collaborative Education Mechanism. The Opinions clearly require that the Home Visitation rules and regulations should be seriously implemented and pointed out the Home Visitations tasks of relevant personnel. It points out that teachers should communicate with parents about the students' situation in a timely manner, help parents keep abreast of the daily performance of students at school. To seriously implement the Home Visitations rules and regulations, school leaders should take the lead in conducting Home Visitation, class advisers should conduct at least one Home Visitation per student per academic year, and subject teachers are encouraged to conduct targeted Home Visitations (Ministry of Education of China, 2023).

As of September 2023, there are 53 junior high schools in Guiping City, Guangxi, China, with 80,844 students and 5,680 teachers, a huge number of students and uneven quality of parents. Coupled with the fact that many students are left-behind children, this group of students, who lack parental companionship and encouragement for a long period of time, may be facing mental health problems and academic problems. Under such circumstances, the pressure on schools to educate students is even greater, and Home Visitations by teachers are even more necessary. Through Teachers' Home Visitations, a harmonious relationship can be established among teachers, parents and students; teachers and parents share the responsibility for education.

In addition, many junior high school teachers in Guiping City, Guangxi are migrants from other cities due to the talent mobility, which lead to a series of challenges during the practice of Home Visitations such as cultural differences, language barriers and unfamiliarity with the local situation of the school, which leads to fear in the Practice of Home Visitations. These are great challenges for novice teachers and young teachers. It is one of the goals of this study to overcome the challenges encountered in the practice of Home Visitations for these teachers, improve the effect of their Home Visitations and promote their professional development.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the Teachers' Home Visitation Practices of junior high school teachers in Guiping City, Guangxi, the challenges the teachers encountered and the actions they made to address the challenges, and then put forward the corresponding Home Visitation plan based on the research results.

Method

The study used quantitative and qualitative design. Chose descriptive design to investigate and analyze the practices of Home Visitations of junior high school teachers in Guiping City, Guangxi and the challenges the teachers encountered in their Home Visitations Practices; and chose phenomenology designs to investigate and analyze the

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actions the participants had made to address the challenges. This study used self-made questionnaires for quantitative research design and semi-structured interviews for qualitative research design. Through questionnaire survey and in-depth interviews with selected participants, this study comprehensively analyzed and deeply understands the practice of Home Visitations of junior high school teachers in Guiping City, Guangxi. After that, the researcher statistically analyzed the data gathered.

The participants in this study were class advisers in the first semester of the 2023-2024 academic year in junior high school of Guiping City, Guangxi. There were 1350 class advisers in the first semester of the 2023-2024 academic year. The researcher used the Convenience Sampling Method to determine that the participants were 338 class advisers.

This study conducted to collect and analyze the data using Likert scale with 5 points. Mean was calculated for each item to analyze the data collected from the survey. The data collected in this study was analyzed by some form of statistical analysis tool, such as Microsoft excel and SPSSAU.

Results and Discussions

This section describes the data collected in the study, analysis and data interpretation.

1. Teachers' Home Visitations Practices

Home Visitation is about socializing and building positive family-teacher partnerships. It involves sharing information about your classroom, filling out forms, and reviewing children's educational progress. In addition to Home Visitations to build relationships and communication, Home Visitation programmes developed over the past few decades specifically focus on teachers educating and supporting parents and children at home (Gestwicki, 2015). Patton (2015) proposed that Home Visitations are a great way for teachers to establish initial contact with students and families, and students will feel safe and comfortable meeting teachers in their own homes.

In China, home is regarded as an important educational place, and it carries a certain range of communication functions, which lays a solid cultural foundation for Teachers' Home Visitations. It can even be said that Teachers' Home Visitations are educational phenomena and activities with China characteristics in the cultural background of China.

As an effective way to establish the cooperation between school and family, Teachers' Home Visitation plays an important role in education. Home Visitation is an important educational means to strengthen the relationship between school and family, enhance the relationship between teachers and students, and promote the effective

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communication between teachers, students, and parents. Through Teachers' Home Visitations, a meaningful parent-child relationship which sees teachers and parents as co-educators with shared responsibilities may be built. This is critical to student's academic success. Home Visitations can not only broaden and deepen Teachers' understanding of students' growth pattern and family education environment, but also establish a relationship of mutual trust, wholehearted cooperation and mutual promotion between schools and families in health education. Through this traditional but effective teaching method, teachers enter students' homes, understand their backgrounds and parents' educational ideas, and discuss students' psychological growth and future development with parents. To achieve the true sense of school-family collaboration, the pursuit of students more scientific, more comprehensive development.

Table 1 presents the average weighted mean and a verbal description of participants' Home Visitations Practices.

Table 1
Summary of Teachers' Home Visitations Practices

Teachers' Home Visitations Practices	Weighted	Verbal
Cognition of the Role of Home Visitation	4.48	Agree
Attitudes towards Home Visitation	3.89	Agree
Preparation before Home Visitation	4.27	Agree
Performance during Home Visitation	4.13	Agree
Post-Home Visitation Action Work	4.40	Agree
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN	4.23	Agree

Legend: (5) 4.51 - 5.00 Strongly Agree; (4) 3.51 - 4.50 Agree; (3) 2.51 - 3.50 Average; (2) 1.51 - 2.50 Disagree; (1) 1.0 - 1.50 Strongly Disagree

As shown in Table 1, it can high degree be clearly found that the participants' Home Visitations Practices has an average weighted mean of 4.23, with a verbal description as Agree, indicating that the participants have high degree of practical abilities in Teachers' Home Visitations Practices. This reflects that Teachers' Home Visitations Practices of junior high school in Guiping City, Guangxi is well implemented.

The participants' Teachers' Home Visitations Practices has an average weighted mean of 4.23, with a verbal description as Agree, indicating that the participants have a high degree of ability of the Teachers' Home Visitations Practices. Among Teachers' Home Visitations Practices, the grand mean of the dimension "Cognition of the Role of Home Visitation" is 4.48, with a verbal description is Agree, indicating that the participants

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have a high degree of Cognition of the Role of Home Visitation. Additionally, the grand mean of the dimension "Attitudes towards Home Visitation" is 3.89, with a verbal description is Agree, indicating that the participants have a high degree of Attitudes towards Home Visitation. Moreover, teachers' Home Visitations Practices in terms of Preparation before Home Visitation has a grand mean of 4.27, with a verbal description as Agree, indicating that the participants have a high practical ability in Preparation before Home Visitation. Furthermore, Teachers' Home Visitations Practices in terms of Performance during Home Visitation has a grand mean of 4.13, with a verbal description as Agree, indicating that the participants have a high practical ability of Performance during Home Visitation. All the other, teachers' Home Visitations Practices in terms of Post-Home Visitation Action Work has a grand mean of 4.40, with a verbal description as Agree, indicating that the participants have a high practical ability Post-Home Visitation Action Work.

Based on their responses, the participants' Home Visitation practices are satisfactory. The Cognition of the Role of Home Visitation and the Post-Home Visitation Action Work got the highest mean, while Attitudes towards Home Visitation and Performance during Home Visitation the two dimensions have slightly lower mean. This shows that school leaders need to formulate more effective policies and strategies to help teachers improve the ability to choose the content of Home Visitations and communicate with parents of students, so as to make their Home Visitation practice more effective. In addition, it is necessary to build a school home visit culture, so that the stakeholders of Home Visitation can understand the importance of Home Visitation more deeply and participate in Home Visitation more actively. By creating a family-school co-education environment, it will help to improve the effect of Home Visitation and provide students with better education.

2. Challenges of the Participants in Their Home Visitation Practices

Teachers are inevitably faced with many challenges when conducting Home Visitations, which cover all levels of schools, teachers, families and communities. Firstly, the school may not be able to fully support teachers to carry out Home Visitations due to factors such as schedule and security. Secondly, teachers may be short of resources and time, so that it is difficult to complete the task of Home Visitation in an all-round way. In addition, the unclear goal of Home Visitation and the imperfect content of Home Visitation may have an impact on the effectiveness of Home Visitation. Thirdly, because parents of students may face life pressures such as work, housework and other obligations, it is difficult for them to communicate with teachers in depth. Finally, due to the differences in community culture and geographical environment, the difficulty of Home Visitations will also increase accordingly.

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Table 2 presents the mean of the challenges participants encountered in their Home Visitation Practice, the grand mean, the verbal description, and the ranking from high to low according to the mean of the challenges.

Table 2 shows the grand mean of Participants' Challenges in Their Home Visitation Practices is 3.84, with a verbal description as Agree. This indicates that the participants have encountered great challenges in their Home Visitation Practice.

As shown in Table 2, the top five challenges are: "Due to the pressure of work and insufficient time and energy, it was difficult for teachers to get a thorough understanding of the family situation", "The students' houses were too far away from the school or the transportation was inconvenient, which made it difficult to implement Teachers' Home Visitations", "Due to the time limitation because of work, housework and other obligations, some parents were unable to communicate with teachers in depth"; "There were insufficient support and services for Home Visitation from schools because of limited human and financial resources", "Some students' parents were not fully aware of the importance of Home Visitations, so they were indifferent to Home Visitations" The mean of the five statements was 4.13, 4.06, 4.02, 3.96, 3.96, respectively, and verbal description for each statement as Agree. It indicates that these challenges are great challenges for participants in their Home Visitation Practice and cannot be ignored. These challenges may make the Practice of Home Visitation more complicated, and how to take appropriate actions to address them is worth thinking about for educators.

Table 2
Participants' Responses as to Challenges in Their Home Visitation Practices

Respondents' Challenges in Their Home Visitation Practices	Mean	Verbal Description	Rank
Due to the pressure of work and insufficient time and energy, it was difficult for teachers to get a thorough understanding of the family situation.	3.68	Agree	1
The students' houses were too far away from the school or the transportation was inconvenient, which made it difficult to implement Teachers' Home Visitations.	3.61	Agree	2
Due to the time limitation because of work, housework and other obligations, some parents were unable to communicate with teachers in depth.	3.57	Agree	3
There were insufficient support and services for Home Visitation from schools because of limited human and financial resources..	3.51	Agree	4
Some students' parents were not fully aware of the importance of Home Visitations, so they were indifferent to	3.51	Agree	5

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Home Visitations.			
The resources of students' village or community were insufficient, so it was difficult to provide corresponding help for Teachers' Home Visitations.	3.47	Average	6
Students were afraid that their parents would beat and scold them after the teacher's Home Visitation, so they resisted the Home Visitation.	3.35	Average	7
Due to the cultural differences between teachers and student parents, the effect of Home Visitations was not good.	3.35	Average	8
Home Visitations were not effective because teachers lacked the relevant professional skills, such as communication skills and problem-solving skills.	3.35	Average	9
Parents were not honest on some information because they were afraid that teachers would treat their children differently when they knew the real family situation.	3.33	Average	10
The effect of Home Visitations was not good because of language barriers in communication between teachers and parents.	3.29	Average	11
Students' parents did not welcome Teachers' Home Visitations for privacy protection.	3.23	Average	13
The students' village or community did not actively cooperate with and participate in Teachers' Home Visitations.	3.23	Average	14
The school did not provide enough Home Visitation training for teachers, and teachers felt uneasy or lacked confidence in Home Visitations.	3.21	Average	15
The school did not have a perfect Teacher's Home Visitation system.	3.20	Average	16
GRAND MEAN	3.39	Average	

Table 2 shows the mean of the other 10 statements is between 3.65 and 3.92, and verbal description for each statement as Agree, which shows that these challenges are great in their Home Visitation Practices. That will greatly affect the enthusiasm and effectiveness of Teachers' Home Visitations, so it needs to be highly valued and taken action to deal with it.

In addition, the participants also supplemented some challenges they have encountered in their Home Visitation Practice. For example: the school does not have a good Home Visitation atmosphere, the school's Home Visitations only to complete the task, resulting in the Teachers' Home Visitations did not achieve the desired effect; Some

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students' parents or students failed to receive Home Visitations at home at the agreed time, but did not inform the teachers, which led to the Teachers' vain trip; Because of the work of teachers and the work of students' parents, it is difficult to determine the Home Visitation time that is suitable for both sides. It is difficult to determine the time of Home Visitations, which Wang found in his study. Wang (2022) pointed out that parents of students have little time and energy to accept Teachers' Home Visitations on workdays, so most parents hope teachers will arrange Home Visitations on non- workdays. Although, for teachers, the free time in non- workdays is more concentrated, which is also conducive to Teachers' better completion of Home Visitations, but a considerable number of teachers think that Home Visitations in non- workdays will occupy their rest time, and work on rest days will not get extra pay, so they are more inclined to arrange Home Visitations in workdays.

Overall, Inadequate Teachers' Home Visitation systems in school, stressful jobs for teachers, busy parents, low community engagement and many other aspects pose these challenges. By investigating and analysing the actions taken by junior high school teachers in Guiping City, Guangxi to deal with these challenges, and summarizing their experience, that can provide experience for other teachers. This has important implications for school administrators, policy makers and teachers.

3. Actions Made by the Participants to Address Their Home Visitation Challenges

Dawa, et al. (2022) pointed out that Home Visitations may vary from school to school and take various forms. Teachers' preference may be different; Some teachers may prefer home visits in pairs, because they may feel more comfortable. Sometimes, teachers also need a translator, that is why they like to pair up. Some teachers like to meet parents one-on-one, while others interact with parents and students at the same time. Similarly, different teachers may take different actions to address the challenges of their Home Visitation Practices.

Through in-depth interviews with 10 junior middle school teachers in Guiping City, Guangxi, the researcher investigated the actions they had taken to deal with the challenges encountered in their Home Visitation Practices. Their shared ideas were summarized and refined as shown in Table 3.

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Table 3

Actions Made by the Participants to Address Their Home Visitation Challenges

Respondents' Challenges in Their Home Visitation Practices	Actions Made by the Participants to Address Their Home Visitation Challenges
<p>Due to the pressure of work and insufficient time and energy, it was difficult for teachers to get a thorough understanding of the family situation.</p>	<p>Made reasonable arrangements for working hours, and communicated with the class adviser and other subject teachers to learn about the academic situation of the students who were going to be visited.</p> <p>Learned from the peer students in the same village or community about the family conditions and other information of the students who were to be visited to improve the efficiency of Home Visitations.</p> <p>Scheduled Home Visitations in winter and summer vacations, weekends and other holidays.</p> <p>Cooperated with other teachers or school administrators to participate in Home Visitations. This allowed more families to be reached in a limited amount of time and to share each other's experiences and insights.</p>
<p>The students' houses were too far away from the school or the transportation was inconvenient, which made it difficult to implement Teachers' Home Visitations.</p>	<p>Conducting Home Visitations during holidays or on weekends could help avoid traffic jams and save time and costs.</p> <p>Worked with organizations such as local communities, village committees or students' parent committees to get access to information to improve the efficiency of Home Visitations.</p> <p>Worked with other educators, social workers, volunteers, etc., and asked them to collaborate on Home Visitations.</p> <p>According to the student's address, plan the Home Visitation route reasonably and arrange the Home Visitation time. For those families that were geographically close to each other, tried to conduct Home Visitations in the same period of time to improve the efficiency of Home Visitations.</p>
<p>Due to the time limitation because of work, housework and other obligations, some parents were unable to communicate with teachers in depth.</p>	<p>Respected the attitudes and decisions of students' parents, understood that they may have their own reasons and difficulties, and provided appropriate support and assistance.</p> <p>Strove to build a trusting relationship with parents. Through friendly and patient communication, show concern and sincerity, so that parents could feel the sincerity and responsibility of teachers.</p> <p>Allowed parents to make appointments with teachers about the Home Visitations according to the actual situation, and</p>

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Respondents' Challenges in Their Home Visitation Practices	Actions Made by the Participants to Address Their Home Visitation Challenges
	informed the teachers in advance of the problems that needed to be solved.
There were insufficient support and services for Home Visitation from schools because of limited human and financial resources.	<p>Made an appointment with other teachers to drive to the same village or community to carry out Home Visitations, and shared the cost to reduce the expenditure of transportation.</p> <p>Teachers could asked colleagues who lived closer to the student's home to help conduct home visits.</p> <p>Teachers could ask for help or support from the local community and agencies, like providing transportation services. In this way, mutually beneficial school-community partnerships could be established.</p>
Some students' parents were not fully aware of the importance of Home Visitations, so they were indifferent to Home Visitations.	<p>Before Home Visitation, teachers could clearly explain the purpose and importance of Home Visitation to students' parents, and stimulated their attention and participation in Home Visitation.</p> <p>In such cases, tried to keep calm and patient, and tried not to let the emotions of students' parents affect the Home Visitations.</p> <p>Strengthened the cooperation between home and school, and strengthened the interaction and communication with students' parents through regular activities such as parent-teacher meetings and symposiums, so as to jointly pay attention to the growth and development of students.</p>
Due to the cultural differences between teachers and student parents, the effect of Home Visitations was not good.	<p>Fully understood the local culture, respected the student parents' cultural habits and values, and avoided behaviours that may violate their cultural taboos.</p> <p>During the conversation with students' parents, teachers could seek common ground with them, such as the importance of education, the expectations of the child's future, etc., to enhance mutual trust and promote the effect of communication.</p> <p>Actively listened to the opinions and ideas of students' parents, remained patient and respectful, and gave enough time and space for them to express their views.</p>
Students were afraid that their parents would beat and scold them after the teacher's Home Visitation,	In the usual education and teaching, established a good relationship of trust with students. By caring and paying attention to students' life and learning, made students feel the love and respect from teachers.

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Respondents' Challenges in Their Home Visitation Practices	Actions Made by the Participants to Address Their Home Visitation Challenges
<p>so they resisted the Home Visitation.</p>	<p>Before planning the Home Visitation, communicated with the students in advance and told them the purpose and the general content of the Home Visitation to reduce the anxiety and resistance of the students. Cooperated with psychological teachers to make home visits when necessary.</p> <p>Teachers could reduce the anxiety and resistance of the students by "customized" Home Visitations. For example, students could write Home Visitation wish cards, choosing topics or places to chat. And during Home Visitations, teachers could bring a small gift like a nice notebook or bag to the student to make them relaxed.</p>
<p>The resources of students' village or community were insufficient, so it was difficult to provide corresponding help for Teachers' Home Visitations.</p>	<p>The school provided some support or resources to the community or village in exchange for their cooperation. For example, provided some educational resources, training or helped solve local problems.</p> <p>Enlisted help from other organizations. For example, contacted local government agencies, NGOs, or volunteer organizations for support and assistance.</p> <p>Contacted acquaintances or friends in the village or community where the students' homes are located and asked them to provide help.</p>
<p>Home Visitations were not effective because teachers lacked the relevant professional skills, such as communication skills and problem-solving skills.</p>	<p>Teachers could actively participate in Home Visitation skill trainings and communication skill trainings, and take the initiative to learn Home Visitation knowledge on the Internet.</p> <p>Teachers could also ask for advice from experienced teachers, accompany them to visit students' homes and observed how they communicated with students' parents.</p> <p>Making reflections on the practice of Home Visitation could also help teachers improve their practice ability of Home Visitation.</p>
<p>Parents were not honest on some information because they were afraid that teachers would treat their children differently when they knew the real family situation.</p>	<p>Teachers could show an equal attitude towards students, made parents know that their children would not be discriminated because of their family situation. Instead, they would pay more attention to students' individual differences and needs, and provided them with more targeted educational guidance.</p> <p>In the process of communicating with parents, teachers could maintain an open and transparent communication attitude.</p>

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Respondents' Challenges in Their Home Visitation Practices	Actions Made by the Participants to Address Their Home Visitation Challenges
	<p>At ordinary times, teachers could maintain regular interaction and communication with students' parents, cared about students' situation, provided necessary help and support, and established a good communication and trust relationship with students' parents, made them feel the sincerity and concern from teachers.</p>
<p>The effect of Home Visitations was not good because of language barriers in communication between teachers and parents.</p>	<p>When communicating with parents, teachers could try to use simple and clear language, avoided using too professional or complex vocabulary. At the same time, spoke slowly to make sure the parents could understand well.</p> <p>Body language could be used to promote teacher-parent communications.</p> <p>Teachers could also conduct Home Visitations with the help of colleagues who spoke the local language or asked volunteers to help translate.</p>
<p>Students' parents did not welcome Teachers' Home Visitations for privacy protection.</p>	<p>Assured student parents that their privacy rights would be respected, emphasized that the purpose of Home Visitations was to better help students by learning about their family background and upbringing environment and providing more appropriate educational support, rather than to explore or expose private information.</p> <p>Assured student parents that teachers would strictly abide by the principle of confidentiality. They would not disclose their family's situation or information at will, would not inquire about the privacy of the family, and would not talk about other parents or students.</p>
<p>The students' village or community did not actively cooperate with and participate in Teachers' Home Visitations.</p>	<p>Tried to connect with community leaders, explained to them the purpose and importance of Home Visitations, and asked for their support and assistance.</p> <p>Tried to speak local language in order to better communicate with local villagers or residents.</p> <p>Used the Internet and other modern scientific and technological means to find relevant information and resources.</p>
<p>The school did not provide enough Home Visitation training for teachers, and teachers felt uneasy or lacked confidence in Home Visitations.</p>	<p>Learned Home Visitation knowledge and skills on the Internet.</p> <p>Learned Home Visitations skills and communication skills from experienced teachers.</p> <p>Doing summaries and reflections on the practice of Home Visitation, including experience and skills.</p>

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Respondents' Challenges in Their Home Visitation Practices	Actions Made by the Participants to Address Their Home Visitation Challenges
	Recommended that schools provided training for teachers on Home Visitation skills and communication skills.
The school did not have a perfect Teacher's Home Visitation system.	Conducted Home Visitations in accordance with educational administration documents. Suggested that schools should develop a Home Visitation system to provide protection for teachers' Home Visitations.

Conclusions and Recommendations

According to the research results and findings, the following conclusions were summarized:

1. Most of the participants have performed well in the Practice of Teachers' Home Visitations. Home Visitation Practices of the participants along cognition, attitudes, preparation before Home Visitation, performance during Home Visitation and post-Home Visitation action work all got high grand mean. The participants had a high degree of cognition, attitude, and practical abilities of Teachers' Home Visitations.

2. Most of the participants have encountered a lot of challenges in their Home Visitation practices. If these challenges are not effectively solved and overcome, they may have a negative impact on the enthusiasm of Teachers' Home Visitation, and further reduce the actual effect and overall quality of Teachers' Home Visitation.

3. A series of positive actions taken by the interviewees in coping with the challenges encountered in the Practice of Home Visitation have provided a deep and enlightening experience for other teachers and educational administrators. It can be seen from these actions that all kinds of challenges encountered in the Practice of Home Visitation need to be solved and overcome by the concerted efforts of schools, teachers, families and communities.

4. A Home Visitation plan to further improve teachers' Home Visitation practice, overcome the challenges in Home Visitation Practice, and improve the effect of Home Visitation was proposed, which consists of the following parts: key results area (challenge), objectives, activities, time frame, requirements, persons involved and expected outcomes.

Based on the results and conclusions of this study, the researcher put forward the following recommendations to promote the effectiveness of Teachers' Home Visitations and improve the quality of education.

1. Education authorities may effectively strengthen the top-level design, theoretical research and scientific management of Teachers' Home Visitations, formulate and improve the Home Visitation system, clarify matters related to Home

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Visitations and countermeasures, and actively carry out training for Teachers' Home Visitations, so as to ensure the effective, efficient and continuous implementation of Teachers' Home Visitations.

2. Each school may in accordance with the national laws, policies, documents and system requirements of the education authorities, and in combination with the actual situation of the school, formulate the work plan for Home Visitations, improve the Home Visitation guarantee mechanism, training mechanism, evaluation and supervision mechanism, build the school Home Visitation culture, and institutionalize, standardize and normalize the Teachers' Home Visitations.

3. Teachers may carefully study the policies and management systems related to Home Visitations, strictly implement the school's Home Visitation policies and requirements, pay full attention to their own professional development, and constantly improve their professional ability and quality, so as to improve the quality and effect of Home Visitations, provide better education services for students and parents, and promote family-school cooperation.

4. Parents, on the one hand, may actively learn about the Home Visitation policies of local education authorities and schools, actively cooperate with teachers' Home Visitation actions, and form educational synergy with schools. On the other hand, it is necessary for parents to take the initiative to understand the child's learning situation at school, truly talk to the teacher the child's learning attitude, lifestyle and behavior habits in the family, and consciously learn from the teacher to deal with the parent-child relationship, improve the child's learning ability, guide the child's psychological issues and other family education knowledge, so as to better promote the child's development.

5. The community may provide strong support for teachers' Home Visitations, sharing community resources, cleaning the community environment, setting up public welfare classes, and preaching family education knowledge. In addition, they may give full play to the coordinating role of village committees and neighborhood committees, and actively cooperate with Teachers' Home Visitations.

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